

What motivates future teachers? The influence of Artificial Intelligence on student teachers' career choice

Judit Martínez-Moreno^{a,b,*}, Dominik Petko^a

^a Institute of Education, University of Zurich, Freiestrasse 36, 8032, Zurich, Switzerland

^b Centre for Education and Digital Transformation, Zurich University of Teacher Education, Lagerstrasse 2, 8090, Zurich, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIEd) is reshaping not only the educational landscape but also potentially influencing the motivations of aspiring teachers. This paper explores whether considerations related to AIEd play a role in student teachers' decision to become teachers. For this aim, the study introduces a new AI subscale within the (D)FIT-Choice scale's Social Utility Value (SUV) factor and validates its effectiveness with a sample of 183 student teachers. Descriptive statistics reveal high mean scores for traditional motivators like Intrinsic Value Teaching, while AI-related factors, although considered, exhibit lower influence. A noticeable disconnection exists between digital motivations and the aspiration to shape the future, suggesting a potential gap in student teachers' understanding of digitalization's future impact. An extreme group analysis reveals a subset of student teachers who significantly consider AI. This group also gives value to Job Security and Make a Social Contribution, suggesting an awareness of AI's societal and professional impacts. Based on these findings, it is recommended to put a focus on teacher education programs to ensure student teachers' understanding of the impact of AI on education and society.

1. Introduction

For decades, researchers have investigated the topic of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIEd) (for example Hofmeister & Ferrara, 1984), but it is in recent years that the field has experienced a significant surge in popularity. This shift in trend is notably attributed to the emergence and widespread adoption of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) tools, such as ChatGPT or DALL-E, both developed by the artificial intelligence research company OpenAI (Williamson et al., 2023). Originally designed for general applications, these tools have entered the educational sphere, which has raised concerns regarding ethics and data protection (Holmes et al., 2023; Ray, 2023). Following the tendency of responding reactively (Schmidt & Tang, 2020), the education sector has put efforts directed towards setting legal and ethical principles to be followed when using these tools, or even designing specific AI tools for the educational context, such as Khanmigo, the teaching assistant from Khan Academy, or the German startup Fobizz which allows the use of GenAI protecting students data privacy.

Amidst these developments, student teachers are right at the heart of this transformative change. It is crucial to assess their awareness of these AI-driven transformations and measure their readiness and eagerness to

actively participate in and shape these changes. By ensuring they are informed and motivated, AI could be better integrated into educational practices, enhancing both teaching and learning experiences.

1.1. Artificial intelligence in education

The scope of opportunities presented by AIEd is extensive, from enhancing students' learning processes to fostering competencies such as critical thinking and problem-solving skills. These benefits extend across various levels and student types, including those with special needs (Kasneci et al., 2023). Specifically, when positioning AIEd as an agent within the educational landscape, Chiu et al. (2023) present various roles that AI assumes across the four educational domains: learning, teaching, assessment, and administration. In the domain of learning, AIEd facilitates individualized learning experiences, engages with students interactively, and provides timely feedback, thereby enhancing adaptability and interactivity. Within the teaching domain, AIEd offers adaptive strategies, supports teacher development, and amplifies pedagogical capabilities. In the assessment sphere, it contributes by automating grading processes and predicting performance outcomes. Finally, in the domain of administration, AIEd plays a pivotal

* Corresponding author. Institute of Education, University of Zurich, Freiestrasse 36, 8032, Zurich, Switzerland.

E-mail address: judit.martinezmoreno@phzh.ch (J. Martínez-Moreno).

role in optimizing platform efficiency, personalizing services, and informing decision-making processes.

The Bhutoria (2022) literature review examined the integration of AI in personalized education across the US, China, and India, revealing AI's significant role in customizing learning to individual needs and transforming the teacher's role from a direct instructor to a facilitator who uses AI to enhance learning experiences. At the same time, challenges such as data privacy, digital resource availability, and accessibility underscore the need for cautious implementation. Chen et al. (2020) also showed that AI used to personalize the educational journey can improve engagement and knowledge retention among students, calling at the same time for cautious implementation due to data privacy concerns. In another study, Yim and Su (2024) examined AI literacy as a goal in the educational landscape, focusing specifically on the K-12 sector. They examined the progress that has been made in AI education over the past two decades and documented a spectrum of learning outcomes that include cognitive, affective, and behavioral domains, as well as course satisfaction and soft skill acquisition.

The transformation of the teacher's role involves adapting to coexist with AI and technology, perceiving these advancements as collaborators rather than antagonists. Educators are increasingly assuming the role of mentors and guides, focusing on the ethical, emotional, and human aspects of learning, while moving away from being "knowledge-holding authorities" (Gentile et al., 2023). At the same time, this change underscores the importance of training and developing AI algorithms to enhance educational practices, highlighting a more integrated and holistic approach to teaching in the digital age (Celik et al., 2022).

In summary, as AI reshapes the educational landscape, it enables educators to adopt more supportive roles and create a more efficient learning environment for students across all levels. However, this progress is accompanied by challenges, including concerns about privacy and the requirement of equitable access to AI resources. The change in the teacher's role is one of the biggest challenges, underlying the need for adaptation and development in this new era of education. Therefore, understanding why student teachers want to assume this role, may give us hints of their readiness to become a teacher in times of digital change.

1.2. Motivations for teaching in the age of AI

There are many drivers for choosing a teaching career, such as the dimensions of the FIT-Choice (Factors Influencing Teacher Choice) model (Watt & Richardson, 2007) which include socialization influences, perceived abilities, perceived demands and returns of being a teacher, fallback career, intrinsic value of teaching, utility value for oneself, and utility value for society. The most mentioned motivations include interest and confidence in teaching, positive prior experiences in the field, commitment to social improvement, and desire to interact and work directly with young people (Watt et al., 2012). These factors capture both personal and societal benefits that motivate individuals toward the teaching profession.

Nevertheless, despite the increasing integration of digital technology in educational settings, few studies have specifically investigated how considerations regarding digital technology can influence the decision to become a teacher (Martínez-Moreno & Petko, 2023; Rana et al., 2021; Rowston et al., 2022). In one of these studies, the (D)FIT-Choice (Digital Factors Influencing Teacher Choice) model was developed as an extension of the FIT-Choice, addressing digital-related factors that shape student teachers' decision to become a teacher (Martínez-Moreno & Petko, 2023). Furthermore, the (D)FIT-Choice scale was developed as an instrument to analyze digital-related motivations to become a teacher.

As AI revolutionizes education and changes the teacher's role, it is key to ensure that teachers are prepared to navigate this shift. Teachers' readiness and intention to embrace AI have been seen as useful in predicting their ability to effectively integrate AI tools into the classroom, as well as predicting their job satisfaction (Wang et al., 2023). Also, the

motivations behind choosing a career in teaching such as perceived teaching ability and intrinsic motivations, like being interested in teaching, have been identified as crucial predictors of professional success, job satisfaction, and the risk of burnout, while extrinsic motivations, such as salary or job conditions, predict stress-inducing thoughts (McLean et al., 2019; Tillmann et al., 2020). These motivations mirror the expectations student teachers hold as they enter the teaching profession (Watt & Richardson, 2007). Moreover, the motivations for adopting AI in education significantly influence teacher retention, addressing a critical concern in the face of a widespread teacher shortage (Alexander et al., 2020; Smethem, 2007). Given this significance, it becomes particularly interesting to investigate whether AIED is among the factors that student teachers consider when deciding to become a teacher. Exploring aspects such as their motivation to use AI for enhancing learning and teaching, or their willingness to use AI to align education with the demands of the digital society, could potentially serve as predictive indicators for anticipating the future adoption of AIED.

One aspect that helps anticipate student teachers' willingness to contribute to society, is the social utility value factor of the (D)FIT-Choice model. This factor considers the motivation of student teachers to become a teacher to shape the future of children and adolescents, enhance social equity, make a social contribution, work with children and adolescents, and contribute to the digital transformation. However, considering AI's profound impact on society, being inclined to use AI can also be seen as a commitment to contributing to societal value. Therefore, the AI-related factors can be considered within the social utility value subscale for two main reasons. On the one hand, AI presents an opportunity to positively impact students' academic journeys through methodologies like personalized learning (Xie et al., 2019). At the same time, it also plays a crucial role in shaping their future. By providing access to curated information, AI facilitates the exploration of professional career options, offering students a valuable perspective on potential paths ahead. On the other hand, the integration of AI into education aligns the learning experience with broader societal trends, incorporating AI applications that have become common in our daily lives (Rane, 2023; Williamson et al., 2023). Furthermore, integrating AI could also help foster critical and ethical reflection on the societal implications of AI (Corrêa et al., 2023). For these reasons, the introduction of AI in education can be perceived as a means of contributing to the overall value of society. Building on the understanding that AI is valuable for society, it becomes desirable for student teachers to demonstrate a willingness to contribute to societal improvement through the thoughtful integration and use of AIED.

1.3. Student teachers' projective, transformative and digital agency

Given the importance of considering AIED to contribute to society, the concept of agency emerges as a key term that provides a framework for using AIED in a way that is consistent with a broader societal contribution. Agency, as Emirbayer and Mische (1998) described, is the capacity of humans to influence the conditions in which they live. More specifically, teacher agency refers to educators' proactive efforts to shape their professional environment and the broader educational landscape, enhancing the overall quality of education (Priestley et al., 2015). This concept is important when considering how individuals' perception of their agency affects their willingness to engage with and adapt to new technologies (Knussen & Agnew, 2022; Siddiq et al., 2023), including AI in education (AIED) and other digital innovations.

Recognizing and fostering agency is fundamental for integrating technologies in education, as it positions teachers as key drivers of educational transformation (Albion & Tondeur, 2018). The concept of digital agency goes further, encapsulating the confidence and skills needed to navigate, interpret, and employ digital technologies effectively in educational settings (Passey et al., 2018). Transformative agency highlights the capacity of student teachers to initiate change

required by the digital transformation (Brevik et al., 2019). Finally, given that student teachers are not yet working in the educational field, their teacher, digital and transformative agency, should be understood along the lines of the projective dimension of agency, focusing on intended long-term actions (Priestley et al., 2015).

In the digital transformation of education, where the consideration of AI contributes to reshaping education, the concepts of teacher, digital, and transformative agency are closely associated with the motivation to contribute to society considering AIEd. This connection suggests that student teachers' consideration of AI in their decision to enter the profession, offers insights into their projective agency in the context of social utility value. Such considerations can provide valuable information about their long-term commitment and orientation toward their future use of technology for societal benefit. Therefore, this study focuses on the consideration of AIEd in the context of social utility value factors as an indicator of student teachers' projective, transformative and digital agency.

1.4. Current study

Given the integration of AI in educational settings and its role in reshaping teacher roles and classroom dynamics, it's essential to explore how these factors influence career decisions among student teachers. The significance of AI in education has been well documented, with studies highlighting its role in personalizing learning, aiding assessment, and administrative functions (Chen et al., 2020; Williamson et al., 2023). More importantly, the ethical and societal implications of AI in education suggest a need for a new generation of educators who are not only proficient in digital competencies but are also critically aware of the ethical implications of its use (Holmes et al., 2023; Ray, 2023). Based on these considerations, in the current study, we investigate the following research question.

RQ1. How relevant is AI in student teachers' decision to become a teacher, by itself and in relation to the social utility value factors?

On the other hand, the heterogeneity in student teacher attitudes toward AI in their professional pathways indicates a need to categorize these perspectives into distinct groups (Thomson et al., 2012; Watt & Richardson, 2008). At the same time, these differences may be related to different professional identity orientations, which was considered relevant in the study of teachers' technology consideration (Lai & Jin, 2021). These differences can also be identified by looking at the representation of other factors across student teachers. Therefore, in the current study, we state the following second research question.

RQ2. How are different levels of consideration of AI represented among student teachers, by itself and across motivational factors?

2. Methodology

2.1. Sample

A total of 183 student teachers in the first semester of their studies answered the questionnaire, which represented a response rate of 65%. These student teachers came from two different universities in Zurich and were enrolled in one of four different programs which are equally recognized throughout Switzerland by the Swiss Conference of Cantonal Ministers of Education: bachelor's degree for primary education (26.2%), master's degree for lower secondary education (19.7%), and master's degree for upper secondary and vocational education at the Zurich University of Teacher Education (10.9%), and master's degree for upper secondary education at the University of Zurich (43.2%). In the latter, one of the authors personally addressed the students to ask them to answer the questionnaire, the other groups were contacted by e-mail.

In terms of gender distribution, 111 participants (60.7%) were

women, 68 (37.2%) were men, 1 (0.5%) would use another term, and 3 (1.6%) opted not to specify their gender. This distribution mirrors the common gender composition observed within samples of student teachers, where women typically outnumber men. The mean age was 28.7 years old (SD = 8.84), and they had a mean of 0.9 years of experience teaching (SD = 4.23). The average teaching experience is less than one year, which means that they may have had previous field experience or be teaching at the time they start their studies. This aligns well with the study's objective of examining individuals whose professional practices and perceptions have not yet been significantly influenced by extensive experience in the teaching field. Yet, this exposure to teaching can facilitate a basic understanding of teaching, potentially leading to more clearly defined reasons for becoming a teacher.

2.2. Procedure and data analyses

The data for this study were collected at the beginning of the teaching studies, concretely in October 2023, in the first month of their programs. The sampling strategy employed for this study is characterized as a convenience sampling method, specifically based on a time-specific approach. This sampling technique was chosen to ensure the collection of data from student teachers at the beginning of their studies to capture their initial perceptions.

Data were collected through an online survey hosted on the LimeSurvey platform and analyzed using Jamovi, version 2.3.21.0 (R Core Team, 2021; The jamovi project, 2022). At the beginning of the questionnaire, participants were greeted with a welcoming message that outlined the study's procedure. Additionally, their data protection rights and right to opt out of the study were explained, allowing them to acknowledge and consent to these terms before proceeding to respond to the questionnaire. In case of doubt, the email addresses of the researchers were provided to clarify any questions. The survey was fully automated, and the participants answered the questionnaire independently.

The first step of this study consisted of the development and validation of the instrument being used. This validation was done through reliability analysis and descriptive statistics using the psych package (Revelle, 2019). This was followed by a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to test the Social Utility Value factor, using the lavaan package (Rosseel et al., 2018). The indices used to evaluate the reliability of the factors were Cronbach's alpha (α) and McDonald's omega (ω), accepting 0.7 as a sufficient measure of reliability (Dunn et al., 2014; Taber, 2018). The indicators used to evaluate the goodness of fit of the CFA were the Bentler Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), the Steiger-Lind Root Mean Square of Approximation (RMSEA), and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). The cut-off criteria were as follows: CFI >0.95; TLI >0.95; SRMR <0.08; RMSEA <0.06 (Hooper et al., 2008; Hu & Bentler, 1999; Schreiber et al., 2006).

After validating the instrument, we proceeded to answer the research questions of this study. For the first research question, descriptive and correlational analyses were used to analyze the relationships between the subscales in the SUV factor. To answer the second research question, extreme group comparisons were performed considering the higher and lower percentiles in AI. For the correlation analysis, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted, and the effect sizes were set at $r = 0.1$ (small), 0.3 (medium), and 0.5 (large) (Cohen, 1992; Plonsky & Oswald, 2014).

2.3. Instrument

The (D)FIT-Choice (Digital Factors Influencing Teacher Choice) scale was used as a starting point (Martínez-Moreno & Petko, 2023; based on Watt & Richardson, 2007). The (D)FIT-Choice scale can be used to better understand the factors influencing the decision to become a teacher in the context of digital transformation. This scale introduced four new factors: Prior digital technology use (within Socialization Influences), Perceived digital teaching competence (within Self-perceptions),

Contribution to the digital transformation (within Social Utility Value), and Intrinsic value subject (within Intrinsic Value).

Given that the (D)FIT Choice does not consider AI specifically, a new subscale was added to the Social Utility Value factor to see if student teachers considered AI when deciding to become a teacher as a factor that contributes to bringing value to society (see Fig. 1, highlighted in blue). In the construction of the AI items, we wanted to capture the different impacts of artificial intelligence (AI) on education. Therefore, the item development centered around five principal considerations: opportunities, challenges, students, teachers, and society. The first item aims to explore the educational opportunities offered by AI (AI1 “I want to use the possibilities of artificial intelligence to improve learning and teaching”). The second item focuses on the student perspective, aiming to foster students’ ability to deal with AI (AI2 “I want to prepare students for the use of artificial intelligence”). The third item examines the alignment of education with society through the consideration of AI, and finally (AI3 “I want to use artificial intelligence to adapt teaching and learning to the digital society”). The fourth item addresses the challenges that AI introduces to the educational landscape (AI4 “I want to address the challenges of artificial intelligence in education”). Finally, the fifth item focuses on teacher agency, delving into educators’ willingness to engage with and contribute to the AI-driven transformation in education (AI5 “I want to contribute to the changes in education brought about by artificial intelligence”). (Table 1)

These items were created through an iterative conceptual process that made the items clearer and more precise each time. This process was based on the previous experience of the authors with questionnaire development. Following the original scale format, the items were designed to address the question, " How important are the following reasons for your decision to become a teacher?". Each item was phrased as a response to the statement, "I chose to become a teacher because ... "

Table 1
Reliability statistics (α/ω) of the (D)FIT-Choice Factors and AI.

Code	Factor	α	ω
AI	Artificial Intelligence	0.94	0.94
PDTC	Perceived Digital Teaching Competence	0.92	0.92
SN	Satisfaction	0.91	0.92
WCA	Work with Children and Adolescents	0.90	0.91
ESE	Enhance Social Equity	0.89	0.89
PTLE	Prior Teaching and Learning Experiences	0.89	0.89
TFF	Time for Family	0.89	0.89
SS	Social Status	0.89	0.89
JS	Job Security	0.88	0.88
SY	Salary	0.87	0.89
CDT	Contribute to the Digital Transformation	0.87	0.87
SI	Social Influence	0.86	0.87
PDTU	Prior Digital Technology Use	0.86	0.87
MSC	Make a Social Contribution	0.82	0.84
JT	Job Transferability	0.77	0.77
PTA	Perceived Teaching Ability	0.76	0.79
EC	Expert Career	0.75	0.76
SFCA	Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents	0.70	0.71
HD	High Demand	0.70	0.72
FC	Fallback Career	0.69	0.76
IVS	Intrinsic Value Subject	0.67	0.72
IVT	Intrinsic Value Teaching	0.65	0.65
SD	Social Dissuasion	0.60	0.64

and had to be answered according to a Likert scale from 1 (not at all important) to 7 (extremely important). The items were created and validated in German, as it is the native language of 94% of the participants, having the remaining 6% a German proficiency level of at least C1, as required by the study programs. Their translation into English for ease of understanding is shown in Table 2.

The instruments reliability and validity were also tested. Reliability

Fig. 1. (D)FIT-Choice model, new factor “Artificial Intelligence”, adapted from Martínez-Moreno and Petko (2023).

Table 2
Descriptive statistics (M, SD) and reliability statistics (α/ω) of AI factor (in bold) and items (α/ω if item dropped).

Code	Items (English translation)	M	SD	α	ω
AI	Artificial Intelligence	4.03	1.61	0.94	0.94
AI1	I want to use the possibilities offered by artificial intelligence to improve teaching and learning.	4.04	1.79	0.92	0.92
AI2	I want to prepare students for working with artificial intelligence.	4.35	1.78	0.93	0.94
AI3	I want to use artificial intelligence to adapt teaching and learning to the digital society.	3.78	1.76	0.92	0.92
AI4	I want to address the challenges of artificial intelligence in education.	4.09	1.89	0.92	0.92
AI5	I want to contribute to the changes in education brought about by artificial intelligence.	3.90	1.76	0.92	0.92

analysis and descriptive statistics were used to assess the internal consistency and validity of the measured factors within this study. Results indicate that most factors have good reliability with Cronbach’s α coefficients ranging from 0.60 to 0.94 and McDonald’s ω coefficients from 0.64 to 0.94 with Social Dissuasion and Intrinsic Value Teaching showing lower levels of internal consistency.

The newly developed Artificial Intelligence in Education factor demonstrates robust reliability, as evidenced by a Cronbach’s α coefficient of 0.94 and a McDonald’s ω value of 0.94, having the highest reliability compared to the other factors. Furthermore, all items contribute to the overall construct of AI as seen in Table 2.

Finally, considering the theoretical assumption that the Artificial Intelligence subscale is under the Social Utility Value (SUV) factor, we conducted a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to empirically assess it. The subscales included under the Social Utility Value (SUV) factor were: Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA), Enhance Social Equity (ESE), Make a Social Contribution (MSC), Work with Children and Adolescents (WCA), Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT), and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The results confirmed the robustness of including the Artificial Intelligence subscale within the Social Utility Value factor, with CFI and TLI higher than 0.95, SRMR lower than 0.08, and RMSEA lower than 0.06 (see Table 3).

Residual covariances added (msc2-msc3, AI3-AI4)

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics and correlations

The first research question explores the relevance of AI in student teachers’ decisions to pursue a teaching career, both independently and in connection with social utility value factors. To address this, descriptive statistics provide a means to contrast AI-related motivations with other influencing factors. For the second part of the question, correlations were conducted to examine the relationship between AI considerations and other social utility values.

When looking at the descriptive results (Table 4), factors such as Intrinsic Value Teaching (M = 6.48), Satisfaction (M = 6.18), and Intrinsic Value Subject (M = 6.11) receive relatively high mean scores, indicating their significance as motivators for choosing the teaching profession. On the other hand, Social Dissuasion (M = 3.26), Prior

Table 3
Fit statistics for the CFA of Social Utility Value (SUV).

X ²	Df	p	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI	
							Lower	Upper
247	153	<0.001	0.962	0.953	0.051	0.058	0.044	0.071

Table 4
Descriptive statistics (M, SD) of the (D)FIT-Choice Factors and AI.

Code	Factor	M	SD
IVT	Intrinsic Value Teaching	6.48	0.56
SN	Satisfaction	6.18	0.90
IVS	Intrinsic Value Subject	6.11	0.76
SFCA	Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents	5.94	0.95
PTA	Perceived Teaching Ability	5.92	0.76
HD	High Demand	5.88	0.81
MSC	Make a Social Contribution	5.78	1.13
EC	Expert Career	5.75	0.88
WCA	Work with Children and Adolescents	5.62	1.18
ESE	Enhance Social Equity	5.55	1.25
PTLE	Prior Teaching and Learning Experiences	5.26	1.43
JS	Job Security	5.14	1.31
SY	Salary	5.04	1.08
TFF	Time for Family	4.54	1.63
SS	Social Status	4.45	1.26
PDTC	Perceived Digital Teaching Competence	4.19	1.43
CDT	Contribute to the Digital Transformation	4.06	1.42
AI	Artificial Intelligence	4.03	1.61
JT	Job Transferability	4.02	1.49
SI	Social Influence	4.01	1.77
SD	Social Dissuasion	3.26	1.41
PDTU	Prior Digital Technology Use	3.22	1.46
FC	Fallback Career	2.44	1.38

Digital Technology Use (M = 3.22), and Fallback Career (M = 2.44) have mean scores below the scale midpoint of 4, therefore, can be considered as having low influence on individuals’ decisions to pursue a teaching career. The other three aspects related to the digital transformation of education, concretely Perceived Digital Teaching Competence (M = 4.19), Contribute to the Digital Transformation (M = 4.06), and especially Artificial Intelligence (M = 4.03) are also among the less influential factors when choosing the teaching profession.

For the correlation analysis, the relationships among all the subscales within the Social Utility Value (SUV) factor (see Table 5) were examined. All variables share some degree of correlation, which was already expected as they belong to the same factor, as previously confirmed through CFA. However, the focal point of interest lies in the level of significance and the effect size of these correlations.

On the one hand, the correlations with high significance ($p < 0.001$) and large effect sizes ($r > 0.05$) are between Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI); and between Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA), Enhance Social Equity (ESE), and Make a Social Contribution (MSC). On the other hand, the lowest correlations ($p < 0.05$) although also with a low effect size (r

Table 5
Correlations between the Social Utility Value subscales (Pearson’s r).

	SFCA	ESE	MSC	WCA	CDT	AI
SFCA	–					
ESE	0.55 ^c	–				
MSC	0.56 ^c	0.62 ^c	–			
WCA	0.31 ^c	0.30 ^c	0.23 ^a	–		
CDT	0.19 ^a	0.24 ^c	0.25 ^c	0.30 ^c	–	
AI	0.17 ^a	0.17 ^a	0.23 ^b	0.21 ^b	0.66 ^c	–

Significance.

^a $p < 0.05$.

^b $p < 0.01$.

^c $p < 0.001$.

< 0.3) are between Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA) and Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT); between Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Enhance Social Equity (ESE); and finally, between Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). Therefore, these results indicate that there is a close connection among the digital-related variables, and among the other social utility value variables. However, the digital-related variables and the rest of the social utility value variables, are not always significantly correlated.

3.2. Extreme group comparisons

The second research question delves into the differences among student teachers concerning their consideration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the decision to pursue a teaching career. This question aims to uncover whether distinct groups of student teachers exist based on the extent to which AI influences their professional choices, and how are other motivational factors represented across these groups.

To analyze differences within the sample regarding AI-related reasons, the dataset was segmented into three distinct groups based on predetermined percentiles. This segmentation aimed to categorize the data into extremes (low and high) and a central group for a comprehensive analysis. Specifically, those data points falling below the 10th percentile (1.60) were categorized as “low”, those above the 90th percentile (6.00) as “high”, and the rest as “middle” (see Table 6).

Considering the variations in sample sizes across the three distinct groups, we opted for the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test. This test indicated significant differences among the medians of the three groups ($X^2 = 83.70$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.46$). Through the Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner (DSCF) pairwise comparisons it was confirmed that all groups were significantly different among them ($p < 0.001$). There were no significant differences between these groups in terms of gender ($X^2 = 0.46$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.79$), age ($X^2 = 2.16$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.34$), years of experience ($X^2 = 4.01$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.13$), or degree level, this is, bachelor’s or master’s degree ($X^2 = 4.64$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.098$).

In the subsequent analysis, Kruskal-Wallis and DSCF were also employed to compare other variables across the three groups (see Table 7). Results show that Perceived Digital Teaching Competence (PDTC), Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT), and Prior Digital Technology Use (PDTU) are significantly different between the three groups ($p < 0.001$). Make a Social Contribution (MSC), Work with Children and Adolescents (WCA), Job Security (JS) and Job Transferability (JT) also show significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$).

Looking at the pairwise comparisons of those factors that are significantly different (see Table 8), Job Transferability (JT) does not show significant differences between the groups. However, there are significant differences in Make a Social Contribution (MSC) and Job Security (JS), with these variables being rated as more important by the group scoring higher on AI-related motives. On the other hand, Working with Children and Adolescents (WCA) is significantly rated as less important by those who score low on AI-related reasons. In the case of Perceived Digital Teaching Competence (PDTC), Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT), and Prior Digital Technology Use (PDTU), these are considered as more relevant for those student teachers scoring higher on AI, and less relevant for those scoring lower.

Table 6
Categorization of AI data based on percentiles.

Group	N	%	Mean	SD
Low	18	9.8	1.07	0.14
Middle	149	81.4	4.12	1.19
High	16	8.7	6.54	0.32

Table 7
Kruskal-Wallis for comparative analysis across AI groups (low, middle, high).

	X^2	df	p	ϵ^2
PDTC	27.72	2	<0.001	0.15
CDT	42.61	2	<0.001	0.23
PDTU	23.21	2	<0.001	0.13
MSC	9.73	2	0.01	0.05
WCA	7.70	2	0.02	0.04
JS	7.02	2	0.03	0.04
JT	6.13	2	0.05	0.03
SI	5.44	2	0.07	0.03
ESE	4.83	2	0.09	0.03
HD	4.80	2	0.09	0.03
EC	4.57	2	0.10	0.02
SD	4.52	2	0.10	0.02
SFCA	4.39	2	0.11	0.02
IVS	3.57	2	0.17	0.02
SY	3.46	2	0.18	0.02
SS	2.75	2	0.25	0.01
IVT	2.68	2	0.26	0.01
SN	1.60	2	0.45	0.01
TFF	1.44	2	0.49	0.01
PTA	0.81	2	0.67	0.01
PTLE	0.72	2	0.70	0.01
FC	0.10	2	0.95	<0.001

Table 8
DSCF pairwise comparisons of significant differences across AI groups (low, middle, high).

	Group (Median)	Group (Median)	W	p
PDTC	Low (2.17)	High (5.00)	5.77	<0.001
	Low (2.17)	Middle (4.33)	6.53	<0.001
	High (5.00)	Middle (4.33)	-3.41	0.04
CDT	Low (2.17)	High (6.00)	6.36	<0.001
	Low (2.17)	Middle (4.33)	6.98	<0.001
	High (6.00)	Middle (4.33)	-6.22	<0.001
PDTU	Low (1.50)	High (4.50)	5.62	<0.001
	Low (1.50)	Middle (3.33)	5.70	<0.001
	High (4.50)	Middle (3.33)	-3.50	0.03
MSC	Low (4.50)	High (6.33)	3.12	0.07
	Low (4.50)	Middle (6.00)	2.51	0.18
	High (6.33)	Middle (6.00)	-3.69	0.02
WCA	Low (4.83)	High (6.33)	3.78	0.02
	Low (4.83)	Middle (6.00)	3.45	0.04
	High (6.33)	Middle (6.00)	-1.42	0.57
JS	Low (5.17)	High (5.83)	3.55	0.03
	Low (5.17)	Middle (5.33)	1.14	0.70
	High (5.83)	Middle (5.33)	-3.41	0.04
JT	Low (3.67)	High (5.33)	2.79	0.12
	Low (3.67)	Middle (4.33)	2.73	0.13
	High (5.33)	Middle (4.33)	-2.13	0.29
WCA	Low (4.83)	High (6.33)	3.78	0.02
	Low (4.83)	Middle (6.00)	3.45	0.04
	High (6.33)	Middle (6.00)	-1.42	0.57

4. Discussion

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is expected to transform the landscape of education, moving it toward a future characterized by AI-enhanced learning experiences. However, this cannot happen by itself. Teachers, standing at the forefront of this educational change, play a pivotal role in aligning their practices with the emerging era of digitalization and AI in education, as well as in implementing AIED appropriately (Celik et al., 2022; Ghamrawi et al., 2023).

In this context, the current study aimed to understand why people choose to become teachers, especially looking at whether the role of AI in education influences those who want to become teachers. For this aim, a subscale for evaluating AI-related factors for becoming a teacher was added to the (D)FIT-Choice scale and validated. Reliability analysis showed that the scale has very good internal consistency in most factors, and Confirmatory Factor Analysis confirmed the robustness of including

the AI subscale within the Social Utility Value factor. These results contribute to the establishment of a reliable measurement tool to analyze student teachers' motives to become teachers in times of digital change concerning AI.

It is however relevant to discuss the two scales that demonstrated low reliability: Social Dissuasion (SD) and Intrinsic Value Teaching (IVT). The following are potential explanations for this finding. On the one hand, Social Dissuasion is a factor that has already shown low reliability before (Martínez-Moreno & Petko, 2023; Watt & Richardson, 2008), being at the same time one of the factors that is assessed as one of the least important. This could lower the reliability of the factor due to a mismatch with respondents' experience, being a factor that is not relevant to them. On the other hand, the low reliability presented by the Intrinsic Value Teaching factor, as seen in previous studies (Watt & Richardson, 2008), contrasts with its typically high reliability in most cases and meta analyses (Navarro-Asencio et al., 2021). Also, given the importance that it has in the decision to become a teacher, its inconsistency is unexpected. However, a plausible explanation might lie in the construct's complexity. As the Intrinsic Value Teaching is a broad factor, it can be interpreted differently by different groups, which could explain the observed discrepancies in reliability.

Regarding the most important reasons that motivate students to become teachers, factors such as Intrinsic Value Teaching (IVT) and Intrinsic Value Subject (IVS) emerge as significant motivators, as seen in previous research (Fray & Gore, 2018; Martínez-Moreno & Petko, 2023). In other words, prospective teachers primarily choose their careers due to intrinsic reasons. However, it is important to approach the interpretation of IVT with caution due to its low reliability in the current study.

4.1. The role of AI in the decision to become a teacher

The first research question aimed to investigate how relevant AI is in student teachers' decision to become a teacher, by itself and in relation to the social utility value factors. Regarding the first part of the research question, results indicate that AI is among the least influential factors when student teachers decide to become teachers. Interestingly, the digital aspects, this means Prior Digital Technology Use (PDTU), Perceived Digital Teaching Competence (PDTC), and Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT), follow a similar trend are and among the least considered factors, as seen in Martínez-Moreno and Petko (2023). Regarding the second part of the research question, looking at the interrelation of various factors, there exists a robust correlation among the social utility digital-related variables Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT). A similar strong relationship among the other social utility value variables Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA), Enhance Social Equity (ESE), Make a Social Contribution (MSC), and Work with Children and Adolescents (WCA). However, these factors present a notably weaker correlation with the factor AI, suggesting a disconnection between willingness to bring value to society for SFCA, ESE, MSC, and WCA, and the consideration of AI as well as CDT. This could indicate student teachers being oriented towards more traditional, non-digital aspects of education and societal contribution (Fray & Gore, 2018). Consequently, this observation suggests that those motivations focusing on long-term impacts on younger generations are rarely influenced by the digital paradigm shift including more transformative trends such as AIED.

In the context of a rapidly evolving educational landscape, as can be seen with the impact of AIED, it becomes crucial to highlight the discrepancy between motivations that are future-oriented, such as those related to SFCA, and those directly tied to digital advancements. This distinction is highly relevant as the future can hardly be understood without taking digital technology into account (Ilori & Ajagunna, 2020; Régo et al., 2023). This discrepancy between the motivation of student teachers and the digital requirements of the future educational landscape could be due to several reasons. A lack of digital literacy may limit student teachers' comprehension of the value of digital tools in

education, subsequently affecting their perception of AIED (Fernández-Batanero et al., 2022; Lim, 2023). Self-efficacy also plays a role in influencing the likelihood of student teachers to consider and adopt AIED and other digital technologies (Lim, 2023; Yeşilyurt et al., 2016).

Furthermore, this raises a significant issue around scalability, the ability to adapt to innovations, one of the technology integration challenges identified by Voogt et al. (2013). Drawing from Coburn (2003), scalability requires substantial modifications in teaching practices (referred to as "depth"), the ability to sustain these changes over time ("sustainability"), the propagation of the innovation across other classrooms and schools ("spread"), and the development of a sense of ownership over the innovation ("shift"). Specifically, the last aspect, "shift", might be missing as student teachers are thinking about how they can make an impact on future generations but are not acquiring a sense of ownership of AIED or other digital technologies for this aim. These results may suggest that student teachers have a reduced perception of their agency – including teacher, digital, and transformative agency –, which can impact their motivation to embrace changes through AIED and other digital technologies (Knussen & Agnew, 2022; Siddiq et al., 2023). This is particularly relevant in the context of the projective dimension of agency, which focuses on the long-term orientation of one's actions (Priestley et al., 2015). However, this perception of agency is something that may change as they begin their professional work as teachers. Finally, contemplating an AI-infused future has also been seen to be key in feeling ready and motivated to shape the future with digital technologies and AIED (Ayanwale et al., 2022; Dai et al., 2020). In summary, addressing this gap requires a comprehensive approach that considers these multifaceted factors influencing student teachers' motivations and perceptions towards AIED in the evolving educational landscape, especially during teacher education programs.

4.2. Student teacher differences in their consideration of AI

The second research question sought to investigate different types of student teachers in terms of their level of consideration of AI when deciding to pursue a teaching career. Notably, while most student teachers consider AI-related factors as unimportant, it is relevant to highlight that there exists a group of prospective teachers who recognize and value the importance of AI-related considerations in their decision to become a teacher. Given these results, it is appropriate to draw parallels with the theory of diffusion of innovations by Rogers (1983), in which the categories of innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards are defined. As seen in this study, many student teachers view AI-related factors as negligible, like the categories late majority or laggards, while a certain subgroup exhibits traits of innovators or early adopters, being eager to consider AI in education. These differences have also been found in previous studies where, for instance, more innovativeness leads to using more AI tools and in a more interactive way (Uzumcu & Acilmis, 2023), or more innovativeness is connected to more positive attitudes toward the use of technology in education (Yilmaz & Bayraktar, 2014).

Furthermore, the findings of this study reveal noteworthy differences in the perceived importance of specific factors among individuals with high levels of AI-related motivations, specifically, they consider Make a Social Contribution (MCS) and Job Security (JS) more important factors. On the one hand, the importance given to MCS could indicate a recognition of the positive societal impact when considering AI, specifically regarding AI in the educational context (Dignum, 2021; Ramesh, 2023). On the other hand, the significance attributed to JS contrasts with the concerns often associated with AI and job automation, which can lead to job insecurity (Malik et al., 2021; Nam, 2019). However, since education is typically viewed as a profession less vulnerable to automation (Frey & Osborne, 2017), and considering the growing need for integrating AI in education (Schiff, 2021; Zhang & Aslan, 2021), it seems that the use of

AI in education can improve rather than threaten the teaching profession. Therefore, considering AI for education can help student teachers feel more confident in their work as teachers. In contrast, Work with Children and Adolescents (WCA) is considered as significantly less important by individuals who score lower on Artificial Intelligence (AI) reasons. This finding indicates that individuals who are less motivated by AI-related aspects, may at the same time prioritize other elements of a career in education over direct interaction with younger age groups.

In conclusion, differences in the importance attached to AI-related factors among student teachers reveal a distinction between those more open and those more resistant to AIED when it comes to becoming a teacher. This polarization also has implications for teacher education, as presented in the next section.

4.3. Educational implications and suggestions

As digital technologies and AI in education (AIED) increasingly find their way into the educational context, teacher education institutions must adapt their programs accordingly (Starkey, 2020). Teacher education is fundamentally about preparing student teachers for their future practice in the dynamic environments they will encounter in schools. In an era where digital technologies are rapidly evolving, it is crucial that teacher education programs also integrate new technologies such as AIED.

However, there is no one-size-fits-all approach to introducing student teachers to these innovations. The results of this study reveal that while most student teachers do not consider AI an important factor when entering the teaching profession, a significant minority do recognize its value. Therefore, institutions should consider differentiated instruction (Ruys et al., 2013; van Geel et al., 2019) by identifying these different groups based on their motivations toward AI to tailor AI integration in a way that resonates with all types of student teachers. This strategy would enable the development of targeted interventions that address the specific needs and motivations of each group.

Given the diverse perspectives that student teachers hold towards AI, these differences can be leveraged to promote collaborative learning (Laal & Laal, 2012), which is often enhanced by group heterogeneity (Dillenbourg, 1999; Yang, 2023). Specifically, it may be beneficial for those who highly value AI to have opportunities to share their ideas with peers who may prioritize more traditional aspects of teaching. This could foster a broader appreciation of the importance of AIED and its impact on education and society among those initially less inclined to consider it.

At the same time, collaborative teaching, also known as co-teaching or team teaching, could be fostered. This approach consists of two or more teachers collaborating and sharing responsibility for planning, delivering, and evaluating a specific course (Decuyper et al., 2023). In the case of student teachers, it could also provide them with opportunities to analyze teaching and learning from diverse perspectives (Vrikki et al., 2021). This collaboration can be influenced by personal characteristics during knowledge sharing, making the differences among student teachers valuable (de Jong et al., 2022). These differences can enhance the critical analysis and sharing of experiences related to digital technologies and AI, enriching the overall learning experience.

Implementing these changes could improve the readiness of the entire cohort of future educators to meet the challenges of a digitally transformed educational landscape, ensuring they develop AI literacy and are well-prepared to integrate AI effectively into their future teaching practices (Hur, 2024; Sperling et al., 2024). However, whether this is the case, should be investigated in future research.

5. Limitations and future research

Despite the insightful findings of this study, it is important to indicate its limitations and identify lines for future research to improve our understanding of the interplay between digital influences and teacher

motivations.

This study relies on a singular time point assessment, using a sample drawn from four cohorts in two Swiss institutions. This introduces limitations in terms of generalizability and the absence of intra-subject reliability testing. To improve the overall generalizability of the findings, future research should emphasize larger and more diverse cohorts, incorporating student teachers from a variety of universities and cultural backgrounds. Also, conducting a longitudinal study with multiple data collection points and interventions would be valuable to determine if motivations evolve. It has been observed that motivations can shift, especially after acquiring experience in school settings (König et al., 2016), and it would be interesting to investigate whether this is also the case for motivations related to AI and the digital transformation of education.

The subscales "Contributing to Digital Transformation" and "Artificial Intelligence" show a high degree of correlation among themselves, which suggests the possibility that these two subscales can be interpreted as components of a broader, cohesive factor that would consider AI as part of digital transformation. This raises the question of whether considering AIED (Artificial Intelligence in Education) as a stand-alone phenomenon accurately reflects student teachers' conception of it. It seems that student teachers might conceptualize AI as an illustrative example of digital technology in education rather than as a distinct entity. While recognizing its greater potential compared to other tools, there may be an inclination to view AI as an integral part of the broader digital landscape in education. This perspective challenges the notion of isolating AIED from broader debates about digital transformation, suggesting that AI is perceived as an advanced iteration within the continuum of educational technologies rather than an entirely separate phenomenon.

Also, in considering future research options, it is essential to address the possible ambiguity in items related to individuals' motivations regarding AIED. Specifically, exploring responses to statements such as "I want to use the possibilities offered by artificial intelligence to improve teaching and learning" could benefit from qualitative interviews to unveil the nuanced and varied interpretations individuals have regarding the potential applications of AI in educational contexts. Similarly, investigating the statement "I want to prepare students for the use of artificial intelligence" would be enriched by exploring the specific challenges respondents perceive students need preparation for in the realm of AI. Furthermore, examining attitudes towards the digital nature of society and AI's role within it, as indicated by the statement "I want to use artificial intelligence to adapt teaching and learning to the digital society" deserves a deeper exploration to understand whether individuals seek alignment or a counterbalance between educational practices and the digital character of society. Also, understanding the challenges of AI in education and mapping the changes brought about by AI, as indicated by statements such as "I want to address the challenges of artificial intelligence in education" and "I want to contribute to the changes in education brought about by artificial intelligence" respectively could be enhanced through qualitative interviews to capture the perspectives shaping these responses.

This study could also be enriched by examining the actual implementation of AI in classroom settings, as well as the level of competence of student teachers. Adopting a comprehensive approach to digital competence, which encompasses knowledge, values, self-regulation, and motivations, as outlined in the COACTIV model (Baumert & Kunter, 2013), would provide a more complete understanding of the factors essential for the effective consideration and use of AI in education.

Lastly, future research should test whether collaborative learning and collaborative teaching approaches enhance digital literacy. Experimental designs investigating these initiatives could identify successful strategies for developing AI literacy.

In summary, it can be said that the current state of AIED is only the initial phase of what is likely to be a long-term development. With this in

mind, the results of this study may serve as a foundation for understanding the initial motivations of student teachers concerning AI. As AI becomes more integrated into educational systems, student teachers' attitudes towards these technologies are likely to change. Therefore, ongoing research is needed to track these changes over time and assess how initial motivations may evolve as AI becomes more integrated into educational practice. This study creates a fundamental point of reference for future comparative analyses.

6. Conclusion

In a changing educational landscape where Artificial Intelligence is shaping education, this study investigates whether student teachers consider these shifts and the influence of AI when deciding to become a teacher. The findings of this study highlight the permanence of traditional reasons to become a teacher, with those motives related to digitality and AI remaining less influential.

The consideration of AI by a group of student teachers reflects their awareness of the social and professional impact that AI will have in the future. However, most student teachers appear to be minimally influenced by the digital transformation in their motivation to become a teacher. The disconnect between digital reasons and motivations for shaping the future raises questions about whether student teachers are aware of the impact that digitization will have in the future.

These findings add to the ongoing call for the preparation of student teachers to deal with both the classical dimensions of education and the challenges presented by a digitally evolving educational landscape. There is a necessity to adopt a balanced and collaborative approach in teacher training programs by developing the required digital competencies, including the development of student teachers' digital and transformative agency while considering the reasons that continue to inspire student teachers.

Declarations on ethics, open data and interest

According to the regulations of the University of Zurich and

Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
(D)FIT-Choice	Digital Factors Influencing Teacher Choice
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIED	Artificial Intelligence in Education
CDT	Contribute to the Digital Transformation
CFI	Comparative Fit Index
EC	Expert Career
ESE	Enhance Social Equity
FC	Fallback Career
FIT-Choice	Factors Influencing Teacher Choice
HD	High Demand
IVS	Intrinsic Value Subject
IVT	Intrinsic Value Teaching
JS	Job Security
JT	Job Transferability
MSC	Make a Social Contribution
PDTC	Perceived Digital Teaching Competence
PDTU	Prior Digital Technology Use
PTA	Perceived Teaching Ability
PTLE	Prior Teaching and Learning Experiences
RMSEA	Root Mean Square of Approximation
SD	Social Dissuasion
SFCA	Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents
SI	Social Influence
SN	Satisfaction
SRMR	Standardized Root Mean Square Residual
SS	Social Status
SY	Salary

(continued on next page)

according to Swiss law, formal approval by the ethics committee was not necessary for this study. Still, informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were aware that their participation was voluntary and could be discontinued at any time without any consequences to their academic, professional, or personal status. Privacy and confidentiality were rigorously upheld throughout the research process. Data was fully anonymized before the data analysis. The dataset generated during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. There are no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Judit Martínez-Moreno: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.
Dominik Petko: Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (GPT-4) and DeepL to improve the readability of the text. While using these tools, the authors constantly reviewed and edited the content as needed. The authors take full responsibility and credit for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

(continued)

Acronym	Meaning
TFF	Time for Family
TLI	Tucker Lewis Index
WCA	Work with Children and Adolescents

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